

**COMPARISONS BY MODULA AND INVESTIGATION OF THEIR PROPERTIES
METHODOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF EXPERIENCE APPROVAL**

Suleymanova K.

*Teacher of the Department of Natural
Sciences and their Teaching Technology
of the Sheki branch of ADPU*

Abstract

It is emphasized in the article that the students who have to study "Algebra" as a compulsory subject got acquainted with concepts such as "set of integers", "division" on this set, "residual division" and solved many tasks related to them. However, there are types of tasks that are difficult to solve. The article evaluates the role of the comparison relationship in the circle of integers, its properties and also the teaching of some related theorems in overcoming such difficulties, in the mental development of students and in the formation of their mathematical creative abilities, and some possibilities of their application in solving mathematical problems with an increasing level of complexity are investigated.

Keywords: comparison, modulus, division with remainder, remainder, comparisons by modulus, subtraction class.

Interpretation of generalizations on research materials. The theory of numbers, which is a source of infinite content and meaning, is the oldest science created by mankind. The brilliant mathematician Carl Friedrich Gauss called mathematics the king of sciences, and calculus its crown. The part of number theory that we will explain in this topic is called classical number theory. Interpreting the information given in this article with the language and terminology of modern mathematics brings not only modernity to the subject, but also clarity and integrity to mathematical facts that seem to be unrelated to each other until now. [5]

If we take any natural number m , then when we divide other integers by it, there will be m different remainders: $0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1$. Let's combine the numbers that give the same remainder when divided by m into one class. Thus, from the "numerical point of view m ", all integers are divided into m different classes. Obviously, the larger m is, the larger the class sets are. Thus, when $m = 1$, there is only one class – the class of integers; When $m = 2$, we get two classes - even and odd numbers, etc.

It should be brought to the attention of students that accounting for the "class structure of society" of integers is useful in solving a number of problems. For example, the expression $(n^3 - n)$ for an arbitrary integer n is divisible by 6.

In the expression of $n^3 - n$, let's take $n - i$ out of the parentheses, and separate the rest using the difference of squares formula:

$$n^3 - n = n(n^2 - 1) = n(n-1) \cdot (n+1) \vee \text{ya } (n-1)n(n+1).$$

It is the product of three consecutive integers that give different remainders when divided by three. Therefore, one of them is necessarily divisible by 3 and at least one by 2. So, the whole product is divisible by $6 = 2 \cdot 3$. (after all, numbers 2 and 3 are mutually prime). If we had more information about the number n , for example if we knew that n is even, we could make more judgments, such as $n^3 - n$ is divisible by 12 or even 24.

It should be emphasized here: It is absolutely not necessary to take m consecutive integers to form a set of numbers from representatives of all the classes that

any number m gives rise to. For this purpose, successive terms of the numerical series $n, n+d, n+2d, n+(m-1)d$ (*) may be suitable, provided that d is prime to m . Indeed, let's look at the difference between the k and l numbers of the sequence (*): $d(k-l)$. Since d is reciprocally prime to m and $|k-l| < m$, $d(k-l)$ is not divisible by m . Therefore, between the terms of this sequence, there are no two that give the same remainder when divided by m .

From the proven theorem, in the special case, it follows that if the numbers m and n are mutually prime, then

$$n, 2n, 3n, \dots, (m-1)n, mn$$

the terms of the sequence give the complete set of remainders from 0 to $m-1$ when dividing by m . To be sure of this, it is enough to write $d=n$ in the sequence (*).

It is possible to illustrate this result geometrically, as the French mathematician Louis Poinson did. Let's number the vertices of the convex m -gon with numbers from 0 to $m-1$. Starting from any vertex, we will go to its other vertices not sequentially, but with n steps, that is, by skipping $n-1$ points. If the interaction with n m is simple, then all vertices: $0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1$ will be traversed until we reach the initial point. If n and m are not mutually prime, we will just pass them through m/D , where D is the greatest common divisor of m and n .

MODULO COMPARISONS AND THEIR PROPERTIES: German mathematician Carl Friedrich Gauss proposed to write the fact that numbers a and b have equal remainders when divided by a natural number m : $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ (read: a and b are compared modulo m). This writing is called comparison. A few examples of comparisons: $-4 \equiv 3 \pmod{7}$; $1997 \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$; $8k+1 \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, where k is an integer. [2]

To be sure that two numbers a and b are comparable modulo b , it is not necessary to find the remainders of dividing each of them by m . It is enough to look at their difference:

• **$A \equiv b \pmod{m}$ if and only if the difference $a-b$ is divisible by m .**

Comparisons reveal properties that are very similar to those of equalities. Equalities can be added to each other, multiplied, one subtracted from the other -

as a result, the correct equality is obtained. The same is true for comparisons:

• **If the arbitrary integers a,b,c,d are such that a is comparable to b and c to d on the modulo m, then the numbers a+c and b+d, a-c and b-d, ac and bd are also comparable on the same modulo m.**

This property can be easily proved if we take the corresponding differences instead of comparisons. For example, let's prove the last property. Suppose $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ and $c \equiv d \pmod{m}$. Then $a-b$ is divisible by m and $c-d$ is divisible by m . But since $ac-bd \equiv a(c-d) + d(a-b)$, $ac-bd$ is divisible by m . Hence, $ac \equiv bd \pmod{m}$, which was also required to be proved.

Raising to a natural power leads to multiplication, therefore: If $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$, then $a^k \equiv b^k \pmod{m}$.

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• **If c and m are mutually prime and $ac \equiv bc \pmod{m}$, then $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$.**

On the other hand, both sides of the comparison can be divided by the same number at the same time as the modulus:

• **If $ac \equiv bc \pmod{mc}$, then $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$.**

Learners should be told that, knowing the properties of comparisons, if we are interested only in the remainder of division by any number m , complex calculus expressions can be simplified. After all, in this case, the arbitrary algebraic expression obtained from integers with the help of addition, subtraction and multiplication can be replaced by the remainders of their division by m , without changing the result.

For example, suppose that when dividing 2^{1997} by 7, it is necessary to know the remainder. It is very difficult to solve this issue directly. The theory of comparisons saves:

$$2^{1997} \equiv (2^3)^{665} \cdot 2^2 \equiv 1^{665} \cdot 4 \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$$

$$10^{70} - 19^2 = 100^{35} - 19^2 \equiv (-8)^{35} - (-8)^2 = -8^{35} - 8^2 = -8^2 \cdot (8^{33} + 1) \pmod{27}.$$

$$8^{33} = (8^3)^{11} = 512^{11} \equiv (-1)^{11} = -1 \pmod{27}.$$

From here

$$10^{70} - 19^2 \equiv -8^2 \cdot (8^{33} + 1) \equiv -64 \cdot (-1 + 1) = 0 \pmod{27} \Rightarrow 10^{70} - 19^2 \div 27.$$

Thus, we proved that the given expression is completely divisible by 27.

Example: As we know, if the digits of the given number are divisible by 9, the number is divisible by 9. Now let's interpret the proof of this through comparison:

$$10^n \equiv 1^n = 1 \pmod{9};$$

$$a = a_n 10^n + a_{n-1} 10^{n-1} + \dots + a_1 10 + a_0 \equiv a_n + a_{n-1} + \dots + a_1 + a_0 \equiv 0 \pmod{9},$$

We have shown above that the relation of comparison is the relation of equivalence. So, this relationship will divide the set of integers into classes. I gave brief information about these classes above. Now let's give detailed information about these classes.

Answer: 4

Another issue: in integers x, y

$$7x - 23y = 1997$$

is required to solve the equation.

To get rid of the sum of $7x$, let's compare the left and right sides of this equation modulo 7:

$$-2y \equiv 2 \pmod{7},$$

Since $7x \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$ and $-23y \equiv -2y \pmod{7}$, $1997 \equiv 2 \pmod{7}$, 3 and 7 are mutually prime, we can multiply both sides of the resulting comparison by 3:

$$-6y \equiv 6 \pmod{7}$$

From here, taking into account $-6y \equiv y \pmod{7}$, we get:

$$y \equiv 6 \pmod{7}$$

So, $y = 6 + 7k$, where k is an arbitrary integer. We get the found value of y by writing in the original equation: $7x - 23(7k+6) = 1997$ and we find that $x = 305 + 23k$. Answer:

$$\begin{cases} x = 305 + 23k, \\ y = 6 + 7k, \end{cases}$$

k is an arbitrary integer.

The theory of comparisons can also be applied to the verification of complex calculations. Let's assume that $1997 \cdot 1999 = 3\,991\,003$ multiplications were made. Let's compare both sides of the obtained equation by 9 modules. This could easily be done using the fact that the number itself and its sum of digits are comparable modulo 9: $1997 \cdot 1999 \equiv 8 \cdot 1 \equiv 8 \pmod{9}$ and $3\,991\,003 \equiv 7 \pmod{9}$, but the comparison was not correct. So there is an error in the calculations. Indeed, the correct answer is $3\,992\,003$.

But in any case, you should take into account: although the background check allows you to detect the error in many cases, it does not guarantee its absence.

Example: Prove: $10^{70} - 19^2 \div 27$

Solution: $10^{70} = 10^{2 \cdot 35} = (10^2)^{35} = 100^{35}$
then

$$100 \equiv 19 \equiv -8 \pmod{27}$$

Suppose that

$$a = \overline{a_n a_{n-1} \dots a_1 a_0}.$$

given. We know that

$$\begin{aligned} A + B^{def} &= \{a + b : a \in A, b \in B\}, \\ A \cdot B^{def} &= \{a \cdot b : a \in A, b \in B\}, \end{aligned}$$

$$n + A^{def} = \{n + a : a \in A\},$$

$$n \cdot A^{def} = \{n \cdot a : a \in A\}.$$

Let us construct the set $[a]_n^{def} = a + n\mathbf{Z}$ for any integer $a \in \mathbf{Z}$. The set $[a]_n$ is called the class of subtractions (comparisons) of the number a modulo n . If $a' \in [a]_n$, then $[a']_n = [a]_n$. Indeed, according to the condition $a' \in [a]_n$, the equality $a' = a + n \cdot p$ must be satisfied for a certain integer p . On the other hand

$$[a']_n = a' + n\mathbf{Z} = a + np + n\mathbf{Z} = a + n(p + \mathbf{Z}) = a + n\mathbf{Z} = [a]_n \cdot [a]_n^{def} = a + n\mathbf{Z}$$

Therefore, each class of comparisons is defined in a one-valued way with any representative of it.

Suppose that the classes $[a]_n$ and $[b]_n$ intersect, that is, $c' \in [a]_n$ and $c' \in [b]_n$. Then $[c]_n = [a]_n$, $[c]_n = [b]_n$. Thus, we get that the intersection of different classes is an empty set. On the other hand, every a is in the class $[a]_n$ of which it is an integer representative. Therefore, the set of classes of fractions given modulo n is a division of the set of integers $\mathbf{Z}$. Let us denote this set by $\mathbf{Z}_n$:

$$\mathbf{Z}_n^{def} = \{[a]_n : a \in \mathbf{Z}\}.$$

Let us denote that the integers p and q are in the equivalence relation caused by this division as $p \equiv q \pmod{n}$. So there exists an integer $a \in \mathbf{Z}$ such that $p, q \in [a]_n$. That is, $p = a + nx$ and $q = a + ny$, hence $n \mid (p - q)$. Note that they usually use the relation $n \mid (p - q)$ to determine the equivalence of $p \equiv q \pmod{n}$.

Let's define addition and multiplication operations on the set $\mathbf{Z}_n$:

$$[a]_n + [b]_n^{def} = [a + b]_n,$$

$$[a]_n \cdot [b]_n^{def} = [a \cdot b]_n.$$

Showing that the determination of the sum and product does not depend on the selection of representatives. Suppose that, $a' \in [a]_n$ and $b' \in [b]_n$ from here $a' = a + np$, $b' = b + nq$, $[a']_n + [b']_n = [a' + b']_n$. By showing that, $[a' + b']_n = [a + b]_n$. Indeed, $[a' + b']_n = a' + b' + n\mathbf{Z} = a + np + b + nq + n\mathbf{Z} = a + b + n = (p + q + \mathbf{Z}) = a + b + n\mathbf{Z} = [a + b]_n$.

Likewise, $[a' \cdot b']_n = a' \cdot b' + n\mathbf{Z} = (a + np)(b + nq) + n\mathbf{Z} = ab + n(aq + bp + \mathbf{Z}) = ab + n\mathbf{Z} = [a \cdot b]_n$.

Therefore, both actions are correctly defined in the set $\mathbf{Z}_n$. $(\mathbf{Z}_n, +)$ is an Abelian group. The zero of this group is the set $n \cdot \mathbf{Z}$.

$$[a]_n + n\mathbf{Z} = a + n\mathbf{Z} + n\mathbf{Z} = a + n\mathbf{Z} = [a]_n.$$

It is clear that in the set $\mathbf{Z}_n$, the distributive conditions of multiplication with respect to addition are satisfied. So $(\mathbf{Z}_n, +)$ is a ring. The class $[1]_n = 1 + n \cdot \mathbf{Z}$ is the unit of this ring. The ring $\mathbf{Z}_n$ is commutative and associative. It can be said that the ring $\mathbf{Z}_n$ retains all the properties of the ring $\mathbf{Z}$ of integers. However, this ring has different characteristics than the rings we have seen so far. Let's get to know them. First of all, the elements of the rings $\mathbf{Z}$, $\mathbf{Q}$ and $\mathbf{R}$ are numbers, but the elements of the ring $\mathbf{Z}_n$ are not numbers, but sets (the class of outputs). Therefore, $\mathbf{Z}$, $\mathbf{Q}$ and $\mathbf{R}$ are called numerical rings. Hence, the number $\mathbf{Z}_n$ is not a ring. Then, while the rings $\mathbf{Z}$, $\mathbf{Q}$ and $\mathbf{R}$ have an infinite number of elements, the ring $\mathbf{Z}_n$ is finite, it has n -number of elements. Here

$[0]_n, [1]_n, \dots, [n - 1]_n$ classes are different, and any class $[a]_n$ is identical to one of these classes (check this). Another distinctive feature will become clear below. Note that if $n = p \cdot q$ is a complex number, this ring has

the following property: $[p]_n \neq 0$, $[q]_n \neq 0$ and $[p \cdot q]_n = [n]_n = 0$.

Therefore, the product of two non-zero elements in the ring $\mathbf{Z}_n$ is zero. Such a ring is called a ring with divisors of zero.

Theorem. $\mathbf{Z}_p$ is the square for an arbitrary prime number p .

Proof. Let p be a prime number. By showing that $\mathbf{Z}_p$ is a square. Let us take an arbitrary nonzero class $[t]_p$ and observe the following results:

$$[t]_p \cdot [1]_p, \dots, [t]_p \cdot [p - 1]_p.$$

Each of these classes is non-zero. Otherwise, an integer q would be found from the numbers $1, 2, \dots, p - 1$ such that $[t \cdot q]_p = [0]_p$. This contradicts the fact that the number p is prime. Obviously, these classes are different. Otherwise, among the numbers $1, 2, \dots, p - 1$, there would be such different q and l that

$$[t \cdot q]_p = [t \cdot l]_p \rightarrow [t(q - l)]_p = [0]_p.$$

Hence, $t \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ or $q - l \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. This is a contradiction. Therefore, the unit is located in one of these classes. So, there is a class $[s]_p$ such that $1 \in [t]_p \cdot [s]_p$, that is, $[t]_p \cdot [s]_p = [1]_p$. So every nonzero class has an inverse.

a and b are integers. the remainder obtained from the division of moment force by b is repeated periodically, starting from a^n certain number.

Since the remainders obtained in the division by b are finite, there are natural powers m and k ($k > m$) such that the equation, $a^m = a^k \pmod{b}$ is fulfilled. Let us accept the notation $t = k - m$. Every natural number n greater than k

$$n - m = qt + r, r < t$$

can be shown as. By showing that

$$a^n \equiv a^{m+rt} \pmod{b}$$

attitude is correct. We will carry out the proof by the method of induction, taking into account q at the stated value of the remainder r . Let's look at the case $q = 1$:

$$a^n \equiv a^{m+(k-m)+r} = a^{k+r} = a^k a^r \equiv a^{m+r} \pmod{b}.$$

So in this case the proposition is true. Suppose the given proposition is true for $q = i$. Let's prove the truth of the proposition for the case $q = i + 1$. Indeed,

$$a^n = a^{m+(i+1)(k-m)+r} = a^{m+i(k-m)+r} a^{k-m} \equiv a^{m+ir} a^{k-m} \pmod{b} \equiv a^{m+ir} \pmod{b}$$

relationships are true. (The fact that the proposition is true for the case $q = 1$ was used in the last passage). This is the required fact.

It is useful to draw up a table of balances in solving the examples.

Example. Find the last digit of 7^{2000} .

The solution. Since the last digit of the number is equal to the remainder obtained from dividing that number by 10, let's make a table of remainders of powers of 7 to 10. To find the remainder corresponding to the value of the next power, you need to multiply the previous remainder by 7 (the base of the power) and divide the result by 10 to find the new remainder:

N	1	2	3	4	5
7^n	7	9	3	1	7

The following is obtained from this table:

$7^n \equiv 1 \pmod{10}$ for numbers of the form $n = 4k$

For numbers of the form $n = 4k+1$ $7^n \equiv 7 \pmod{10}$

For numbers of the form $n = 4k+2$ $7^n \equiv 9 \pmod{10}$

For numbers of the form $n = 4k+3$ $7^n \equiv 3 \pmod{10}$

N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
3^n	3	4	2	1	3	4	2	1
7^n	2	4	3	1	2	4	3	1
$3^n + 7^n$	0	3	0	2	0	3	0	2

In other words,

For numbers of the form $n = 4k$, $3^n + 7^n \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$

For numbers of the form $n = 4k+1$, $3^n + 7^n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$

For numbers of the form $n = 4k+2$ $3^n + 7^n \equiv 3 \pmod{5}$

For numbers of the form $n = 4k+3$, $3^n + 7^n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$

In a special case, the relationship $3^{2005} + 7^{2005} \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ is true for the power $n = 2005 = 4 \cdot 501 + 1$. That is, $3^{2005} + 7^{2005}$ is divisible by 5 without remainder.

In comparisons, the simple case of the module is especially distinguished. It is useful to begin the transfer of information about this element to students with the introduction of the following theorem:

Fermat's Little Theorem: If p is a prime number, the relation holds for any natural number n . In other words, the remainders obtained from the division of n^p and n by p are equal.

This theorem makes it easy to solve many examples. Let's look at an example.

Example. Let's find the remainder of 1967^{1985} by 13.

The solution. $1985 = 152 \cdot 13 + 9$ or $1967 = 151 \cdot 13 + 4$

$$\begin{aligned} 1967^{1985} &\equiv 1967^{152 \cdot 13 + 9} \pmod{13} \equiv \\ 1967^{152 \cdot 13} \cdot 1967^9 &\pmod{13} \equiv 1967^{12 \cdot 13 + 5} \pmod{13} \equiv \\ 1967^{12 \cdot 13} \cdot 1967^5 &\pmod{13} \equiv 1967^5 \pmod{13} \equiv 4^5 \pmod{13} \equiv \\ 10 &\pmod{13} \end{aligned}$$

In the 2nd, 3rd and 4th comparisons, Fermat's little theorem was applied.

One of the most important theorems related to comparisons is Euler's theorem.

Theorem: If $m > 1$ and $(a, m) = 1$, that

$$a^{\varphi(m)} \equiv 1 \pmod{m}$$

Many examples become easier to solve by applying this theorem:

Let's find the remainder obtained from dividing the number 1237^{427} by 44. Since $1237 \equiv 5 \pmod{44}$, we get: $1237^{427} \equiv 5^{427} \pmod{44}$. Since $(5, 44) = 1$ and $\varphi(44) = 20$

In the special case, when $n = 2000$, $7^{2000} \equiv 1 \pmod{10}$ is obtained. That is, the last digit of the number 7^{2000} must be 1.

Example. Prove that the sum $7^{2005} + 3^{2005}$ is divisible by 5.

The solution. Let's make a joint table of the powers of 7 and 3 and the remainder of their sum to 5.

Since, we get from Euler's theorem:

$$\begin{aligned} 5^{20} &\equiv 1 \pmod{44} \\ 1237^{427} &\equiv 5^{427} \equiv 5^{20 \cdot 21 + 7} = 5^7 \equiv (-7)^2 \cdot 5 \\ &\equiv 5 \cdot 5 = 25 \pmod{44} \end{aligned}$$

so the answer is 25. [1]

It should be clear to the students that, applying Euler's theorem, it is not necessary to draw a table of remainders if the modulus is a prime number. More precisely, it is possible to solve tasks quickly and easily by applying Euler's and Fermat's theorems.

Conclusion: Modulus comparisons are very important in mathematics. Thus, the solution of many examples becomes easier by applying the properties of the comparison relation of the set of integers and related theorems. Therefore, it is important to study the importance of this topic in mathematics and its applications.

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